

BOILING POINTS OF MONOHALOGEN DERIVATIVES OF NORMAL PARAFFINS

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Relationship between the boiling points of normal paraffins and their monohalogen derivatives has been studied. It has been found that the difference between the squares of the boiling points of a normal paraffin and its monohalogen derivative is a constant. The constant is different for different halogens.

In a previous communication (Varshni, this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 535) a formula correlating the boiling points of the various members of the normal paraffins had been suggested.

A simple relationship has been found to exist between the boiling points of a normal paraffin and its monohalogen derivative, which can be represented by the formula:

$$T^2 - T_x^2 = K$$

where T and T_x are the boiling points (in degrees absolute at 1 atmos.) of the paraffin and the corresponding monohalogen derivative, and K is a constant. The results are recorded in Table I. The values of K for chloro, bromo and iodo derivatives are respectively 48900, 65330, 87720.

TABLE I

Paraffin.	T.	Monochloro			Monobromo			Mono-iodo.		
		T_x		Error.	T_x		Error	T_x		Error.
		(obs.)	(calc.)		(obs.)	(calc.)		(obs.)	(calc.)	
Methane	111.5	248.9	247.7	-1.2	276.56	278.86	+2.3	315.5	316.5	+1
Ethane	184.7	286.3	288	+1.7	311	315.3	+4.3	345.2	349	+3.8
Propane	230.9	319.7	319.7	0	343.9	344.3	+0.4	375.4	375.5	+0.1
Butane	272.6	351.7	351	-0.7	374.6	373.7	-0.9	404	402.5	-1.5
Pentane	309.1	380.3	380.1	-0.2	402	401.1	-0.9	429	428.2	-0.8
Hexane	342	407.1	407.3	+0.2	429	427.1	-0.9	453	452.4	-0.6
Heptane	371.5	432.6	432.4	-0.2	451.8	450.9	-1.9	475.95	475.05	-0.9
Octane	397.6	456.1	456	-0.1	474	473.7	-0.3	Decomposes		

The difference between the calculated and observed values of T_x does not exceed 1.5 % in any case. In most cases it is well below 1 %.

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